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A REVIEW: HERBS USED AS ANTI OBESITY AGENTS

***Badri.Nagarani**, Subal debnath, Nilesh P. Babre, Santhosh Kumar C.
Srikrupa Institute of Pharmaceutical Sciences,
Vil. Velkatta, Mdl: Kondapak, Dist. Medak, Siddipet, Andhra Pradesh – 502 277, India.

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ABSTRACT

Since the time immemorial plants have been in use as sources of medicine throughout the world. The demand for plant-based medicines is ever growing as crude or processed products from plants have less or no adverse effects. Obesity is a global epidemic and most common disorder in the world. Obesity refers to an abnormally high proportion of total body fat. It results from less physical work and more mental work existing, in our present day living and working conditions. Traditional herbal medicines have more acceptance than prescriptional drugs in many cultures with epidemics of obesity. Here an attempt has been made to discuss about the antiobesity activity of various herbal plants. In India most of the people is facing the problem of obesity. Garlic, Guggul, pride of India, Nutmeg, Black Pepper, Tamarind are the most commonly used herbal drugs in India for the treatment of obesity due to effective decrease in cholesterol synthesis. Cabbage an excellent home remedy for obesity due to the presence of a valuable chemical tartaric acid present in this vegetable which inhibits the conversion of sugar and other carbohydrates into fat. Piperine is the active principle found in Black pepper which will reduce the levels of plasma total cholesterol, low density lipoprotein (LDL), very low-density lipoprotein (VLDL).

Corresponding author

Badri.Nagarani, Srikrupa Institute of Pharmaceutical Sciences,
Vil. Velkatta, Mdl. Kondapak, Dist. Medak, Siddipet,
Andhra Pradesh - 502 277, India.
E-mail: subal_2007@yahoo.co.in,9949402406.

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Introduction

Obesity is a medical condition in which excess body fat has accumulated to the extent that it may have an adverse effect on health leading to reduced life expectancy on health or increased health problems. Obesity is one of the leading preventable causes of death worldwide. A sedentary life style plays a significant role in obesity. Worldwide there has been a large shift towards less physically demanding work and currently at least 60% of the worlds population gets insufficient exercise due to increased use of mechanized transportation. An average obesity reduces life expectancy by 6 to 7 years. Obesity is from lattan word *obesitas*, which means stout, fat or plump. The causes for obesity is High glycemic effect,genetic disorder, eating disorder, stressful mentality and Insufficient sleep.

Herbal sources of antiobesity

Prickly Chaff Flower(*Achyroathus aspera*)¹: It belongs to the family Amaranthaceae. It is an annual or perennial herb. It is found throughout tropical Asia, Africa, Australia and America. The alcoholic extract of this plant at 100 mg/kg dose reduces total serum cholesterol (TC) and phospholipid (PL), triglyceride (TG) and total lipid (TL) levels. This cholesterol lowering activity might be due to rapid excretion of bile acids causing low absorption of cholesterol. Hence it is used as antiobesity agent.

Garlic (*Allium sativum*)¹: It belongs to the family Alliaceae. It is a small herb. It is a native of central Asia and occurs all over India. S-allyl cysteine sulfoxide is the active principle found in this plant. It showed inhibitory effects on transaminases, alkaline phosphatase lipogenic enzymes and HMG CoA reductase and stimulatory effects on plasma lecithin cholesterol acyl transferase lipolytic enzymes and fecal excretion of sterols and bile acids. Further studies showed that the S-allyl cysteine sulfoxide treatment also reversed the lipid peroxidation and decreased reduced glutathione levels, superoxide dismutase and catalase activities. Garlic protein (16% of diet) and garlic oil (100 mg/kg/day) exhibited significant lipid lowering effects in rats fed with cholesterol diet. The hypolipidemic action is primarily due to a decrease in hepatic cholesterogenesis.

Sweet flag (*Acorus calamus*)¹: It is belongs to the family Araceae. It is a semi-aquatic, perennial, aromatic herb with creeping rhizomes. It is found throughout India in damp marshy places. Investigations revealed that the presence of tannins in this plant is responsible for hypolipidemic activity. Tannins from this plant at 10mg/kg dose decreased the serum cholesterol and triglyceride levels.

Veld Grape (*Cissus quadrangularis*)¹: It belongs to the family Vitaceae. It is a Succulent vine. It occurs throughout India. The antiobesity effect is due to reduction in plasma TBARS and carbonyls. They also brought significant reductions in weight, body fat, total cholesterol, LDL-cholesterol, triglycerides, and fasting blood glucose levels.

Karpuravali (*Coleus forskohlii*)¹: It belongs to the family Laniaceae. It is a perennial member of the mint family. It grows in India, Nepal, Sri Lanka, and Thailand. Forskolin, a diterpene is the active principle found in this plant. Forskolin is the unique adenylate cyclase activating phytonutrient. Adenylate Cyclase is an enzyme that activates Cyclic Adenosine Monophosphate (cAMP) in the cell. Cyclic AMP promotes the breakdown of stored fats in animal and human fat cells. It regulates the body's thermogenic response to food, increases the body's basal metabolic rate, and increases utilization of body fat. It may also release fatty acids from adipose tissue, which results in increased thermogenesis, loss of body fat, and theoretically increased lean body mass.

Guggul (*Commiphora mukul*)¹: It belongs to the family Burseraceae. It is a small tree or shrub. It occurs in Rajputana, Khandesh, Berar, Mysore, Sind and Baluchistan. The stereoisomers E-and Z guggulsterone have been identified as the bioactive compounds. These compounds are antagonist ligands for the bile acid receptor farnesoid X receptor which is an important regulator of cholesterol homeostasis. It is likely that this effect accounts for the hypolipidemic activity of these phytoosteroids . A recent study demonstrates that guggulsterone upregulates the bile salt export pump (BSEP), an efflux transporter responsible for removal of cholesterol metabolites, bile acids from the liver.

Such up regulation of BSEP expression by guggulsterone favors cholesterol metabolism into bile acids, and thus represents another possible mechanism for its hypolipidemic activity.

Brindal Berry (*Garcinia cambogia*)¹: It belongs to the family Guttifera. It is a small or medium-sized tree. It occurs in the evergreen and shola forests of Western Ghats in India. Hydroxycitric acid(-) is the active ingredient of the fruit and the rind of this plant. It competitively inhibits the extramitochondrial enzyme adenosine triphosphate-citrate (pro-3S)-lyase. This enzyme ensures the supply of acetyl-CoA, which is used by acetyl-CoA carboxylase, the regulatory enzyme of lipogenesis in the liver. This is also important in the regulation of biosynthesis of endogenous lipids, levels of plasma lipoproteins VLDL (very-low-density lipoprotein), LDL (low-density lipoprotein) and HDL (high-density lipoprotein) and the distribution of the lipid in extra hepatic tissues, especially adipocytes, the storage site of body.

Cabbage(*Brassica oleracea var. capitata*)²: It is considered to be an excellent home remedy for obesity. A valuable chemical tartaric acid present in this vegetable which inhibits the conversion of sugar and other carbohydrates into fat. Hence it is in great value in weight reduction. Substituting a meal with cabbage salad is a simplest way to stay slim.

Green tea(*Camellia sinensis*)²: It is a natural stimulant that much behaves like coffee but with the added vitamin c and flavonoids (compounds that are antioxidants).

Ephedra(*Ephedra sinica*)⁵: It contains the amphetamine like substance ephedrine and is the natural form of phenyl propanolamine (PPA). Ephedrine in combination with caffeine and aspirin results in a small but significant weight loss.

Nomame Herba (*Cassia nomame*)⁵: It inhibit lipase activity, reduced weight gain and elevation in triglycerides when fed a high fat die.

French Lilac (Goat's Rue, *Galega officinalis*)⁵: Galega is well known for its hypoglycaemic action. Galega has a novel weight reducing action in mice, is largely independent of a reduction in food intake.

The mechanism of wt. reducing action is unclear but involves loss of body fat.

Gudmar (*Gymnema sylvestree*)⁶: It belongs to the family Asclepiadaceae. It is a woody climber. It is found in the Deccan Peninsula and western India. The active compound of this plant is a group of acids termed as gymnemic acids. It has been observed that there could be a possible link between obesity, Gymnemic acids and diabetes. *G. sylvestree* leaf extract reduced the elevated serum triglyceride (TG), total cholesterol (TC), very low-density lipoprotein (VLDL)- and low-density lipoprotein (LDL)-cholesterol in a dose-dependent manner. The decreased serum high-density lipoprotein (HDL)-cholesterol and antiatherogenic index (AAI) in hyperlipidaemia were also reversed towards normalization. The ability of this extract (at 100 mg/kg) to lower TG and TC in serum and its antiatherosclerotic potential were almost similar to that of a standard lipid lowering agent-clofibrate.

Indian Sarsaparilla (*Hemidesmus indicus*)⁶: It belongs to the family Asclepiadaceae. It is prostrate or semi-erect shrub. It is distributed throughout India. In vivo studies showed that 2-hydroxy 4-methoxy benzoic acid (HMBA) is the bioactive molecule using ethanol-induced experimental model of hyperlipidemia. Oral treatment of HAMBA at 200 microg/kg-1 was shown to significantly reduce the ethanol-induced elevated plasma and hepatic levels of total cholesterol, triglycerides, lipoproteins, phospholipids and free fatty acids in rats. This was accompanied by elevated lipoprotein lipase.

Roselle (*Hibiscus sabdariffa*)⁶: It belongs to the family Malvaceae. It is an annual/Perennial shrub. It is native of West Indies and is now cultivated in Uttar Pradesh, Andrapradesh, West Bengal, Bihar, Punjab, Assam and Tamilnadu. Hibiscus acid and its 6-methyl ester were respectively isolated as active principles. Aqueous extract of dried calyces of *H. sabdariffa* showed significant decrease in plasma glucose and cholesterol.

Pride of India (*Lagerstroemia specios*)⁶: It belongs to the family Lythraceae. It is a deciduous tree. It is found in many parts of Southeast Asia including the Philippines, India, Vietnam, Malaysia and southern China. Both alpha- and beta- penta-O-galloyl-D-

glucopyranose (PGG), components of tannic acid are responsible for the adipogenesis inhibitory activity exhibited by this plant extract [39] and by tannic acid. This plant extract had a significantly reduced body weight (~10%) in obese mice.

Bitter Gourd (*Momordica charantia*)⁶: It belongs to the family Cucurbitaceae. It is a slender, climbing annual vine. It is cultivated all over India. 5% lyophilised Bitter melon (*M. charantia*; BM) powder showed decreased adipose tissue mass, TAG content and glycerol-3-phosphate dehydrogenase activity when supplemented with high-fat diet. This implies that BM might reduce lipogenesis in adipose tissue. Rats also showed significantly lower mRNA levels of fatty acid synthase, acetyl-CoA carboxylase-1, lipoprotein lipase and adipocyte fatty acid-binding protein implying that BM can reduce insulin resistance effectively. Thus BM can suppress the visceral fat accumulation and inhibit adipocyte hypertrophy, which may be associated with markedly down regulated expressions of lipogenic genes in the adipose tissue.

Nutmeg (*Myristica fragrans*)⁷: It belongs to the family Myristicaceae. It is an aromatic tree. The plant is a native of Moluccas, now cultivated in many tropical countries of both hemispheres. In India, it is grown in Tamil Nadu. The ethanolic extract of this plant extract demonstrated significant hypolipidaemic effects in experimentally induced hyperlipidaemia in rabbits. It lowered the lipoprotein lipid levels, total cholesterol, LDL cholesterol and triglycerides. HDL cholesterol was not significantly affected. Total cholesterol, HDL and LDL: HDL ratios were also significantly lowered. It lowered the level of total cholesterol in the heart and liver and demonstrated platelet antiaggregatory activity. Seed extract administration reduced both total and LDL cholesterol, lowered the cholesterol/ phospholipid ratio and elevated the decreased HDL ratio significantly in hypercholesterolemic rabbits. This extract also prevented the accumulation of cholesterol, phospholipids and triglycerides in liver, heart and aorta and dissolved atheromatous plaques of aorta.

American ginseng (*Panax ginseng*)⁷: It belongs to the family Araliaceae. It is a perennial herb. It grows naturally on well drained mountainous

hardwood forests. It is cultivated in Korea, Japan, China, Russia and Germany. Protopanaxadiol (PD) and Protopanaxatriol (PT) of saponin fraction are the active principles of this plant. It was reported that the administration of crude saponin (CS) from RG (200 mg/kg, i.p.) for 3 weeks reduced the weight of the body, the parametrical adipose tissues and the levels of serum Lipid and leptin in the HF diet fed rats. Red ginseng saponin fractions, PD and protopanaxatriol PT reduced the body weight, total food intake, fat contents, serum total cholesterol and leptin to levels in the high fat diet induced rats. The hypothalamic expression of Orexigenic neuropeptide Y was significantly decreased with PD or PT treatment, whereas that of anorexigenic cholecystokinin was increased. In addition, PD type saponins had more potent antiobesity properties than PT saponins, indicating that PD type saponins are the major components contributing to the antiobesity activities of ginseng crude saponins. Therefore the antiobesity activity of PD and PT type saponins may result from inhibiting energy gain, normalizing hypothalamic neuropeptides and serum biochemicals related to the control of obesity. P. ginseng therapy improved psychophysical performance and reduced fasting blood glucose and body weight in diabetic patients. Ginseng has been widely used as the remedy for such life-style-related diseases such as arteriosclerosis, hyperlipidemia, hypertension and non insulin-dependent diabetes mellitus, and there are many reports on the pharmacological effects of ginseng.

Japanese ginseng (*Panax japonicus*)⁷: It belongs to the family Araliaceae. It is a perennial herb. It is also known as Japanese ginseng and is cultivated in Japan. Chikusetsusaponins are the active principle found in this plant. The rhizomes of *Panax japonicus* are used as a folk medicine for treatment of lifestyle related diseases such as arteriosclerosis, hyperlipidemia, hypertension and noninsulin dependent diabetes mellitus as a substitute for ginseng roots in China and Japan. It has been used as a substitute for Ginseng root. Total chikusetsusaponins isolated from *P. japonicus* prevented high-fat-diet-induced increases in body weight and fat storage in adipose tissue. They inhibit intestinal absorption of dietary fat through the inhibition of pancreatic lipase activity, and the active components were identified here as chikusetsusaponins III and IV, 28-deglucosyl chikusetsusaponins IV and V.

Black Pepper (*Piper nigrum*)⁷: It belongs to the family Piperaceae. It is a branched climbing perennial shrub. It is cultivated in the hot and moist parts of India, Ceylon and other tropical countries. Piperine is the active principle found in this plant. Piperine supplementation reduced the levels of plasma total cholesterol, low density lipoprotein (LDL), very low-density lipoprotein (VLDL) and the activity of 3-hydroxy 3-methyl glutaryl coenzyme A (HMG CoA) reductase in the liver, heart and aorta, VLDL and significantly ($P < 0.05$) elevated the levels of plasma and tissue lipoprotein lipase (LPL) and plasma lecithin cholesterol acyl transferase (LCAT) in high fat diet fed male wistar rats. Simultaneous supplementation of piperine significantly ($P < 0.05$) enhanced fecal excretion of bile acids and neutral sterols implying that piperine can prevent the accumulation of plasma lipids and lipoproteins significantly by modulating the enzymes of lipid metabolism.

Ceylon lead root (*Plumbago zeylanica*)⁷: It belongs to the family Plumbagenaceae. It is a perennial, sub-scandent shrub. It is found wild in peninsular India. Ethanolic extract (50% v/v) of root, alone and in combination with vitamin E, significantly reduced serum total cholesterol, LDL cholesterol and triglyceride levels in experimentally induced hyperlipidaemic rabbits. However, Dwivedi, pointed out that the ethanolic extract of *P. zeylanica* root alone and with vitamin E lowered HDL cholesterol levels as well. The plain (single drug) made of chitraka root if taken orally in dosage of 2-3 pills twice a day for about 3 months with luke warm water or butter milk, results in reducing excessive lipid levels in blood i.e. reduces obesity. The root powder taken orally along with honey gradually reduces hypercholesterolemia and improves blood formation.

Brinjal (*Solanum melongena*)⁸: It belongs to the family Solanaceae. It is a small tropical perennial. It is a native of Africa and Asia. Flavonoids are the active principles in this plant. Flavonoids extracted from the fruits of *S. melongena* (Brinjal) showed

significant hypolipidemic action in normal and cholesterol fed rats. The fresh, ripe fruits of *Solanum melongena* and *Solanum gilio* significantly reduced serum total cholesterol. These observations demonstrated that they have strong hypolipidemic effect and is an indication of the possible use of this fruit in the treatment of diseases associated with hyperlipidemia and arteriosclerosis.

Tamarind (*Tamarindus indica*)⁸: It belongs to the family Fabaceae. It is a large tropical tree. It is cultivated and naturalized in the tropics throughout the world. Oral administration of aqueous pulp extract of this plant resulted in a dose dependent decrease in body weight of rats. The decrease in body weight may be attributed to the reduction in food and water intake caused by chemicals that affect brain centers involved in satiety and hunger or could have inhibited digestive enzymes or decreased bioavailability of nutrient caused by anti nutritional factors present in plant extract. Dose dependent decrease in body weight could also be attributed to the presence of anti nutritional factors like saponins in the extract.

Fibers (Psyllium, Plantago, Guar fibers)¹⁶: Several studies support the use of fiber to promote weight loss. Fiber remains in the gut and thus may increase subjective feelings of fullness and decrease food intake. Large amounts of fiber can cause gastrointestinal distress recommended for weight loss.

Caffeine¹⁶: Caffeine obtained from guaraná (*P. cupana*), kola nut (*Cola nítida*), or yerba mateit stimulates fat breakdown via sympathetic receptors and is often added to weight loss products for its thermogenic effect (Bray, G.A., 2000). Most clinical studies include caffeine as a co-ingredient with agents such as ephedra. This makes it hard to separate the independent effect of caffeine. In 1991, the FDA banned caffeine as an additive to non-prescription weight loss products because it had not been proven effective

Table 1: Lipase inhibitory effects of various chinese herbs³

Sr. No	Scientific name	Plant part	Family
1	<i>Achyranthes bidentata</i> Bl	Root	Amaranthaceae
2.	<i>Alisma oriental</i> (Sam.) Juzep.	Tuber	Alismataceae
3.	<i>Angelica sinensis</i> (Oliv.) Diels.	Root	Umbelliferae
4.	<i>Astragalus membranaceus</i> (Fisch.) Bunge	Root	Leguminosae
5.	<i>Atractylodes macrocephala</i> Koidz.	Rhizome	Asteraceae
6.	<i>Bupleurum chinense</i> DC.	Root	Umbelliferae
7.	<i>Carthamus tinctorius</i> L.	Flower	Asteraceae
8.	<i>Citrus aurantium</i> L.	Young fruit	Rutaceae
9.	<i>Cornus officinalis</i> Sieb. Et Zucc.	Fruit	Cornaceae
10.	<i>Dioscorea opposita</i> Thunb.	Rhizome	Dioscoreaceae
11.	<i>Eclipta prostrata</i> L.	Whole grass	Asteraceae
12.	<i>Ephedra sinica</i> Stapf	Herbaceous stem	Ephedraceae
13.	<i>Epimedium brevicornum</i> Maxim.	Aerial part	Berberidaceae
14.	<i>Forsythia suspensa</i> (Thunb.) Vahl	Fruit	Oleaceae
15.	<i>Grataegus pinnatifida</i> Bunge	Fruit	Rosales
16.	<i>Leonurus japonicus</i> Houtt.	Fruit	Labiatae
17.	<i>Ligusticum chuanxiong</i> Hort.	Rhizome	Umbelliferae
18.	<i>Ligustrum lucidum</i> Ait.	Fruit	Oleaceae
19.	<i>Millettia reticulata</i> Benth.	Rattan cane	Leguminosae
20.	<i>Morus alba</i> L.	Ear	Moraceae
21	<i>Paeonia lactiflora</i> Pall.	Root	Ranunculaceae
22.	<i>Panax notoginseng</i> (Burk.) F.H.Chen	Root	Araliaceae
23.	<i>Phragmites communis</i> Trin.	Rhizome	Poaceae
24.	<i>Pinellia ternata</i> (Thunb.) Breit.	Tuber	Araceae
25.	<i>Plantago asiatica</i> Linn.	Whole grass	Plantaginaceae
26	<i>Polygonum cuspidatum</i> Sieb. et Zucc.	Root and rhizome	Polygonaceae
27.	<i>Polygonum multiflorum</i> Thunb.	Root	Polygonaceae
28.	<i>Portulaca oleracea</i> Linn.	Aerial part	Portulacaceae
29.	<i>Prunella vulgaris</i> L.	Ear	Labiatae
30	<i>Pueraria lobata</i> (Willd.) Ohwi	Root	Leguminosae
31.	<i>Raphanus sativus</i> L	seed	Cruciferae
32.	<i>Rheum palmatum</i> L.	Root and rhizome	Polygonaceae
33.	<i>Salvia miltiorrhiza</i> Bge.	Root and rhizome	Labiatae
34.	<i>Saposhnikovia divaricata</i> (Turcz.) Schischk.	Root	Umbelliferae
35.	<i>Sophora tonkinensis</i> Gapnep.	Root and rhizome	Leguminosae
36.	<i>Taxillus chinensis</i> (DC.) Danser	Aerial part	Loranthaceae
37.	<i>Uncaria macrophylla</i> Wall.	Aerial part	Alismataceae

Banana (*Lagerstroemia speciosa* Linn. Leaves)¹⁷: Extracts from banana leaves have been reported to reduce diabetic symptoms in genetically diabetic mice. Banana had a beneficial antiobesity effect on obese female KK-A^y mice. This effect was due to a reduction in the accumulation of triglyceride.

Tobacco (*Nicotiana tabacum*)¹⁷: Nicotine isolated from tobacco leaves (*Nicotiana tabacum*) increases

metabolism, decreases food intake. It increases fat oxidation and energy expenditure, an effect limited to time of exposure and more prominent in normal than overweight subjects.

Guduchi (*Tinospora Cordifolia*)¹⁹: It is a commonly used herb for treatment of obesity. It helps in reducing fats in the body and is very effective in weight loss.

Guggul²⁰: Guggulhills is a very effective herb for controlling obesity & cholesterol. It possesses strong purifying and rejuvenating properties. It is also useful in arthritis, effective in blood circulation etc.

CONCLUSION: The present review summarises plant derived botanical and dietary supplements which are widely prescribed worldwide and are considered natural, safe and beneficial for the treatment of obesity. Obesity has been the problem in the affluent societies of developing and developed world. Hence the diseases which are common manifestations of obesity are prevalent in obese persons. The anti obesity action commonly reported among guggulsterone, gymnemic acids which involves reduction in the elevated serum triglyceride (TG), total cholesterol (TC), very low-density lipoprotein (VLDL)- and low-density lipoprotein (LDL)-cholesterol in a dose-dependent manner. S-allyl cysteine sulfoxide is the active principle found in Garlic plant. It showed inhibitory effects on transaminases, alkaline phosphatase lipogenic enzymes and HMG CoA reductase and stimulatory effects on plasma lecithin cholesterol acyl transferase lipolytic enzymes and fecal excretion of sterols and bile acids.

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